

Prehistoric Coastal Environments in Greece: The Vanished Landscapes of Dimini Bay and Lake Lerna

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Two completely vanished environments in Greece, a shallow coastal bay at Dimini near Volos and a large freshwater lake near Lerna south of Argos, were found and reconstructed with over 200 auger and drill cores. Similarities between the coastal landscapes of modern Volos and Argos with respect to topography and settlement history are attributable to comparable geological settings and Holocene environmental histories; for example, at both places active faulting has played a significant role and shoreline shifts have determined site locations. Near Volos the sea extended 3 km farther inland during the middle Holocene, reaching the base of Dimini Magoula (tell). After the Neolithic the shore gradually receded, resulting in a seaward shift of settlements, thus explaining the presence of several single-component sites in the area. Near Argos, the former presence of a large freshwater lagoon, named Lake Lerna, has been deduced from subsurface deposits. The lake was separated from the open sea by a beach barrier. It originated when the postglacial sea level rise reached its culmination point and extended over a diameter of 4.7 km in the Early Bronze Age. Increased soil erosion then caused a rapid silting, but remnants of Lake Lerna persisted until the last century. Anthropological studies have shown how the inhabitants of this coastal marsh have suffered from malaria in the past. It may be that the story of the legendary fight between Herakles and the Lernaean Hydra reflects the struggle of the Lernaean people as they tried to change the inhospitable environment by draining the lake.

Introduction

In order to understand the interrelation of cultural and landscape evolution and to determine to what extent cultural change was environmentally influenced, it is necessary to study key areas where extensive landscape changes as well as early and rapid cultural development took place concurrently. The evidence of prehistoric anthropogenic environmental change might then be used as a guide for the investigation of culturally-generated environmental change in the present. This study presents coastal landscape reconstructions of two areas of prime archaeological importance whose settlements have played a key role in the cultural development of Greece during the last 8000 years.

Greece is especially suitable for prehistoric landscape reconstructions because of its complex coastline, its sensitive and marginal climate, its active tectonism and resulting diverse geomorphology, and most importantly because the earliest complex archaeological cultures on the European continent occurred in Greece. Coastal landscapes represent a sensitive interface for environmental changes, since the position of the shoreline is easily shifted

in response to eustatic sea level oscillations, sediment infill, or tectonic displacement. What is more, coastal plains have a high preservation potential and information about previous landscapes is preserved by burial.

Today's archaeologists are well aware that settlement patterns are just one component of past environments that continuously evolved through the interaction of nature and man (Shackley 1979: 429; Butzer 1982). Environmental archaeology and the study of site patterns therefore necessitate reconstructions of past landscapes which must correspond in their degree of accuracy to the archaeological knowledge of the area in question. Because the field of geoarchaeology is still in its infancy, however, such landscape reconstructions are rarer than archaeological surveys and settlement pattern studies.

The landscape reconstructions of the modern Bay of Volos and the Argive Plain are discussed together here because they are in many respects alike, in particular with regard to their geological setting and archaeological significance. Although the Argive Plain is 25 times larger than the coastal plain of Volos, both areas are rich in arable land and are fed by ephemeral streams and fringed

by steep, barren, limestone mountains. Both have been of great strategic importance in the past, as is demonstrated by the prominent sites and cities of Lerna, Mycenae, Tiryns, Midea, Argos, and Nauplion in the Argive Plain and Dimini, Pevkakia-Magoula, Petromagoula, Iolkos, Demetrias, and Volos on the Gulf of Volos. In both cases the favorable nature of the setting was recognized by early inhabitants, who in the Neolithic had already established regionally important settlements. Although both areas grew in importance by serving as bases for military powers and/or as trade ports in the Late Bronze Age, and subsequent Classical, Hellenistic, and Medieval periods, within the plains the centers of settlement shifted from one locality to another (Marzloff 1981: 118), possibly because of environmental changes, as one area of the coastal plain became more favorable for living than another. Sunken constructions, including harbors, are known at Demetrias (Marzloff 1980) and from the Argive Plain (Curtius 1851: 49, 384; Lehmann 1937: 22), and both areas contain Mycenaean citadels which are assumed (Iolkos) or known (Tiryns: Finke 1988a: 138) to have been closer to the sea when they were inhabited. Thus shoreline shifts have had relevance for site function and distribution, making the coastal plains a suitable target for a holistic reconstruction of the landscape.

The primary objective of this study was to determine whether the comparable archaeological histories of the two areas resulted from their similar geological and topographical settings. Secondly, landscape reconstructions were expected to explain why the centers of population shifted several times in history at both places and whether the archaeological settlement patterns, as found today, have been altered by recent geological processes such as erosion, superposition, tectonic displacement, and sea level change.

Geoarchaeological Approach

Every conceivable source of data by which environmental parameters may be recorded must be considered in order to achieve an accurate picture of past landscapes. This includes the archaeological history as well as zoological and botanical remains, human remains, climate and vegetation history, the history of land use, reports by early travellers, historical engravings, old landscape photographs, and satellite images. The prime sources of information, however, are the present topography, which is the product of previous landscape changes, and the Holocene subsurface stratigraphy, in which evidence of past landscapes is preserved. The topographic analysis is based on 1:5000 scale maps and satellite imagery; the stratification was examined in natural and man-made exposures (river

and road cuts, construction pits, quarries, archaeological excavations) and, where those were absent, on auger and power drill cores. For a detailed description of field and laboratory methods employed during these projects, see Finke (1988a).

A total of 12 months of fieldwork was conducted in the regions of Volos and Argos in 1982 and 1984–1987, during which over 200 cores were taken. Comprehensive reports of this work have appeared in two unpublished theses (Finke 1984, 1988a) and preliminary results in several short reports (Finke 1987a, 1987b, 1988b, 1988c; Zangger 1989).

The Present Gulf of Volos and Ancient Dimini Bay

The area around the modern port of Volos has long been a preferred living area. Marzloff (1980) attributes this to the protected situation of the bay within the Pagasean Gulf, a circumstance that favored both military operations and far-reaching trade. In the Neolithic, the Bay of Volos (FIG. 1) provided the nearest access to the sea for the numerous sites in the Thessalian plain (Weisshaar 1989). The importance of the area is marked by such prominent ancient settlements as Sesklo, Dimini, Petromagoula, Pevkakia-Magoula, Iolkos, and Demetrias. The Early Neolithic site of Sesklo lies 8 km from the present coast and was inhabited from ca. 6000–4400 B.C. by possibly 3000–4000 inhabitants (Theocharis 1973: 68). Dimini sits on a natural knoll 18 m above sea level, 3 km west of the present coast; excavated in 1903 by Christos Tsountas, it was inhabited from 3700–3000 B.C. (Theocharis 1973). Petromagoula, an Early Bronze Age settlement on the southern margin of the plain, has been excavated since 1981 (Chatziangelakis 1984). Another excavation at Pevkakia-Magoula by Milovjic and Hiller has uncovered a deep, stratified site inhabited since the Middle Neolithic (Marzloff 1981: 126; Weisshaar 1989). In the Late Bronze Age, Pevkakia-Magoula was closely related to Iolkos which, although essentially unexcavated, is known to have been an important Mycenaean citadel. Much later, in 294–288 B.C., the city of Demetrias was established at Pevkakia-Magoula, which Demetrios Poliorketes identified as the capital of an empire that extended along the entire Aegean coast, including Asia Minor (Marzloff 1981: 128). Demetrias soon declined but regained importance in the Roman period. Today the region is dominated by Volos, one of Greece's largest port cities.

Single-component sites and sites that have not been inhabited throughout the area's entire cultural history are

Figure 1. Map of the coastal plain near Volos with the location of archaeological sites in relation to paleo-shorelines. Sesklo lies 5 km west of Dimini outside the map. When Dimini was established in the Late Neolithic, the sea extended more than 3 km farther inland. In the Early Bronze Age (3000 B.C.) the shore had already regressed more than halfway to its present location. At that time Petromagoula was founded where the sea extended farthest inland. In 300 B.C. (Hellenistic period) both ends of the long wall of Demetrias reached the sea. Black dots indicate core sites, the thin line through the plain marks the location of the cross section (FIG. 2), and the dashed line marks the trend of a normal fault that traverses the plain (after Finke, 1987a).

surprisingly abundant, indicating that the regional centers must have shifted from one part of the coastal environment to another (Marzloff 1981: 118). A working hypothesis for a landscape reconstruction could be that a stable landscape will be reflected in the existence of sites with long sequences of settlements, while single-component sites, or those at which settlement was short-lived, suggest an instable landscape.

Regional Geology

The mountain range between Albania and Asia Minor, called the Hellenides by Kober (1929), is divided into several paleogeographic units, striking NNW-SSE, that began as drifting and colliding continental fragments in the former Tethys Sea (Jacobshagen et al. 1978). During the Mesozoic several shallow-water platforms were separated from each other by small seas underlain by oceanic crust. Collision of the African and European continents resulted in the subduction of the ocean basins and the convergence of the platforms.

Several regional geological investigations have covered the area around Volos (see Schneider 1968; Ferrière 1976,

1982; Wallbrecher 1983), and the Greek Geological Service recently published the geological map of the region. The area around Volos belongs to the Pelagonian zone of the Central Hellenic Nappe and consists of Permian to Jurassic platform sediments on a consolidated Variscan substrate. At the end of the Jurassic the platform became covered with pelagic sediments; later olistostromes and the Eohellenic nappe¹ were superimposed onto it followed by flysch² in the Cretaceous and early Tertiary. Around Volos, strata of conglomerates, albite-gneiss, and epidote-albite-phylite underlie thick, slightly metamorphic and, upwards, increasingly dolomitic limestone; these units correspond to Wallbrecher's (1983) subdivision of the Pelagonian zone on the southern Pelion Peninsula and the northern Sporades into calcite and dolomite marbles, phylites, and gneiss.

Recent block faulting has dissected the bedrock and shaped the present topography. Two main normal faults define the coastal plain of Volos: one parallels the main road from Velesinon to Volos on the north side of the valley, the other one coincides with the steep limestone slope on the southern side of the coastal plain. Current tectonic activity on these faults is indicated by deeply incised ravines near Sesklo (shown in Theocharis 1973: 28) and by a number of magnitude 6 earthquakes that have struck Volos during the last century (Schneider 1968: 72; Papazachos et al. 1983).

Holocene stratigraphy

The coastal plain of Volos (FIG. 1) consists of Holocene floodplain alluvium deposited during ephemeral floods by streams entering the plain from the north and the west. Pleistocene alluvial fans and colluvial deposits restrict the alluvium to a 3 km-wide plain between Dimini and the coast. Buildings were constructed only on consolidated pre-Holocene rocks, whereas the Holocene floodplain is exclusively used for agriculture and its limits are clearly discernible from a distance by the dark green color of the dense vegetation.

The Holocene stratigraphy was determined from 31 auger cores of up to 11.5 m depth. Thick, extensive gravel deposits from streams which descend from Pelion inhibited hand augering in the northern part of the floodplain. Most cores are therefore located in the southern half, where the silty alluvium is only occasionally interbedded with stream gravel, and these cores establish a cross-section from the present coast to Dimini. A threefold stratig-

1. A large, sheet-like rock unit that has moved on a predominantly horizontal surface, usually through thrust faulting.

2. A marine sediment characterized by a sequence of thinly-bedded deposits of marls, sandy shales, and muds.

Figure 2. Auger core section across the floodplain of Volos. The bottom layer consists of fine-grained reduced marine deposits extending to the base of Dimini, where they develop a lagoonal character (clay-rich, gley color, abundant organic material). The marine mud is covered by silty backshore deposits and floodplain alluvium laid down by ephemeral stream floods. A normal fault can be seen in the profile, displacing the deposits, including a gravel layer and a wood layer.

raphy, which could be correlated from core to core, was found in this traverse (FIG. 2).

(1) Marine deposits: a few boreholes located 2–3 km inland bottomed in Pleistocene paleosols or bedrock; most cores, however, terminated in a fine-grained, bluish gray (5BG4/1)-to-black reduced mud containing marine fossils. This buried marine layer below the floodplain alluvium extends approximately 3 km inland of the present coast, indicating that the sea used to extend much farther landward almost all the way to the Neolithic site of Dimini. The macrofossil fauna preserved in these marine deposits (*Cerastoderma edule*, *Nucula nucleus*, *Gastrana fragilis*, *Venerupis perforans*, *Abra alba*, *Gibbula magus*, *Bulla striata*, *Bittium reticulatum*, *Rissoa similis*, *Cyclope neritea*, *Turboella pulchella*) in combination with the microfossil fauna (*Ammonia beccarii*, *Elphidium crispum*, *Aubignyanella cf. mariei*, *Cibronion cf. translucens*) allows a reconstruction of the past submarine environment: the assemblage reflects a Mediterranean shallow, warm-water biotope with a muddy bottom and abundant algae (Daniels 1970). Farther inland the deposit gradually changes to a clay-rich lagoonal facies in which plant remains dominate over marine fossils.

(2) Backshore deposits: the upper boundary of the marine mud is marked by a sharp color change to brownish yellow (10YR6/6). Grain size and microfossil content remain unchanged until approximately 50 cm above the reduced marine mud; from there on the marine fossils cease

to be present. This well sorted, thinly laminated, fine-grained deposit originated in a backshore environment similar to that inland of the present beach.

(3) Alluvium: the unstratified floodplain silt that overlies the backshore deposits averages 3 m; it formed during floods of the ephemeral streams and contains shells of the terrestrial snail *Helicella italata*. Locally, the floodplain alluvium is interbedded with well-rounded and well-sorted stream gravel deposited by the ephemeral streams Seskolithis and Xerias, the latter having a large drainage system on the south side of Mount Pelion.

The anaerobic environment of the marine deposits permits the preservation of wood fragments suitable for conventional radiocarbon dating that has yielded calibrated dates between 6000 and 5000 B.P. (Finke 1984; Taylor 1984: 22). From these dates, the rate of deposition can be estimated as 1–2 m/1000 years, a normal one for a coastal plain environment. Assuming that the surface angle of the alluvium has not changed over the last few millennia, the rate of regression can be calculated. After the transgression had reached its culmination point, the coast must have retreated quickly to about halfway to its present location; it then slowed down because the increasing water depth required larger amounts of sediment infill.

The boundary between the reduced marine mud and the floodplain deposits is horizontal on the eastern side of the cross-section and close to present-day sea level. Farther inland, however, it drops sharply in two steps by 3.1 m,

then slowly rises again toward Dimini. These steps result from a set of normal faults that cross the traverse, displacing both the wood layer and a gravel horizon (FIG. 2). One of the two faults produced a displacement of 1.7 m before it was covered with undisturbed alluvium and must have ceased activity about 3000 years ago. Movement on the second fault resulted in a displacement of 1.4 m and affects the alluvium as well; it thus cannot be older than ca. 1000 years. These faults are responsible for the steep slope of the limestone hills south of the coastal plain and extend westward from Pevkakia-Magoula over Petromagoula to Paliouri, a village south of Dimini that has been deserted because of the earthquake hazard. Essentially all earthquakes around Volos are attributed to such E-W striking normal faults and typically reach a magnitude of 6, resulting in a vertical displacement of 1 m in a single event, with movement along a 10–15 km-long fault (James Jackson, personal communication, 1989). The most recent earthquake in this area reached magnitude 6.5 and struck the town of Almyros in 1980; it was caused by a normal fault that parallels the one found in the cores (Papazachos et al. 1983).

Even if the displacement on each of the two faults in the section took place in a single event, it did not result in an incursion of the sea, because no marine sediment is intercalated in or superimposed on alluvium. Figure 3 shows the depositional history of Dimini Bay and how the faulting occurred after the regression had essentially run its course.

Reconstruction of Dimini Bay

At the end of the last glaciation the melting of the polar ice caps led to a global sea level rise of ca. 120 m (Fairbanks 1989). Coastal plains, at places many kilometers wide, were flooded by the advancing shoreline (e.g., van Andel and Shackleton 1982). New natural harbors came into existence in drowned estuaries, one of them being Dimini Bay, where the beach was situated near the knoll on which Dimini began to flourish at ca. 3500 B.C. (FIG. 4). At that time Dimini Bay was U-shaped (FIG. 1) and contained a shallow-water, fully marine biotope that was populated by typical Mediterranean low-energy coastal fauna.

Radical environmental change came to Dimini Bay late in the Neolithic. The transgression had reached its maximum and the knoll became settled, but habitation continued only as long as the shore remained near the foot of the hill. Thus the site location and possibly the function of the site seem to have been closely related to its environmental setting. Marine shells, still found in large numbers on the surface of the site, indicate that the sea played

Figure 3. Depositional history of Dimini Bay. During the maximum transgression in the Neolithic, the sea stretched landward to Dimini. Soil erosion and redeposition caused a swift regression. When the first subsidence took place, the marine mud was already covered by backshore deposits. The regression continued after the faulting. During the second subsidence a residual gravel layer originating from the first off-set and the floodplain alluvium was displaced (after Finke 1984).

a major part in the livelihood of the inhabitants. The soils in the hilly terrain may have been exploited for the first time (van Andel and Runnels 1988: 239) and while the shore was still at its peak position and Dimini was thriving, soil erosion increased in the hinterland and the eroded soils gradually filled Dimini Bay. During this phase of soil instability an extensive layer of decomposed wood was deposited in the shallow bay. The wood provided radiocarbon dates of 4000–3000 B.P. It was transported to the bay from upstream and may record the effect of the Dimini Culture on its environment: conversion of the forests into fields by slash and burn cultivation could explain both the wood layer and the soil erosion. The silting up of Dimini

Figure 4. Reconstruction of Dimini by M. Korres (Theocharis 1973) modified by the addition of the Neolithic coastline.

Bay resulted in a rapid withdrawal of the sea. The bay, initially 1–2 m deep, rapidly filled with coarse stream-gravel deposits coming from the steep, eroding Pelion slope, and with fine-grained material brought by the Seskolitis River from the west. Although the sea has continued to rise (at a lower rate) until the present day, this rise was overcompensated by sedimentation. Thus the coast has regressed continuously, but as the supply of soil vulnerable to erosion became exhausted, and because the sea increased in depth with distance from the shore, the regression gradually slowed.

In the Early Bronze Age the sea had receded by ca. 2 km; where it reached farthest inland the site of Petromagoula was established. This place may have been preferred over the knoll at Dimini because of its position at the coast, considering the advantages gained by easier and more rapid transport of goods, access to marine food

resources, etc. (Runnels and van Andel 1988). Here, too, marine shells found in the excavation (mainly *Murex brandaris* and *Trunculariopsis trunculus*) point to the importance of the sea as a resource for the Early Bronze Age inhabitants. But once again, the desirability of the setting was only temporary; as the coastline continued to recede the site became deserted. In Hellenistic times the shore was just a few hundred meters landward of its present position and the city wall of Demetrias, beginning at the beach, encircled the whole peninsula and city (FIG. 1), leaving its northern side open to the sea.

Pevkakiya-Magoula and Iolkos, on the other hand, have not been affected by environmental changes. The sea between the modern port of Volos and Pevkakiya-Magoula has always been open, although the relatively steep slopes on the southern and northern side of the valley allow only a narrow waterway. Also because of the steep slope, coast-

Figure 5. Map of the southern Argive Plain showing the location of prehistoric sites, the paleo-coastline at maximum transgression (2500 B.C.), and the former expanse of Lake Lerna. The NW-SE trending line through Magoula and Lake Lerna marks the position of the cross section in Figure 7, while the w-E trending line in northern Lake Lerna marks the profile in Figure 8.

line changes near Iolkos have been negligible. Thus Iolkos and its successor, Volos, were situated on a spot that has remained environmentally favorable for at least 3500 years. In conclusion, although site locations are not necessarily determined by the environment alone, and factors governing site selection may have changed over time, the position of the coastline in the Bay of Volos appears to always have been an important parameter influencing site locations.

The tectonic activity in the coastal plain had no great effect on the physiography. The submergence of the inner plain did not cause a transgression, because sedimentation rates exceeded the tectonic subsidence as well as the slight eustatic sea level rise. Because of the fault, however, the topography of the coastal plain is asymmetrical, the lowest part being on the far south side at the base of the limestone slopes.

The Present Gulf of Argos and Ancient Lake Lerna

The charm of the Argive Plain (FIG. 5) is largely due to the contrasting landscape at the NW end of the Gulf of Argos, where mountains, several hundred meters high, drop steeply into the sea. The crests of the Artemision Mountains are often covered by snow, while at their feet the only perennial stream of the eastern Peloponnese turns the plain into a green, densely overgrown meadow, which contrasts sharply with the dry and more typically Greek landscape of gently rolling hills on the east side of the Argive Plain.

Excavations in Kefalari Cave have shown that this picturesque landscape has been exploited since the latest Middle Paleolithic (Reisch 1980; Perlès 1987; Runnels 1988). Settlement at Lerna began in the 6th millennium B.C. and lasted until the 1st millennium B.C. (Caskey 1960; see also

Runnels 1985: 357). Clearly the site was chosen because of its setting near fresh water, fertile arable land, and the sea. Although little is known about the site of Magoula, emergency excavations in the 1970s have shown that it is an extensive prehistoric settlement with deep occupational deposits (Hope Simpson and Dickinson 1979: 246; Catling 1980: 28).

The Lake

Early travellers, including Pausanias in the 2nd century A.C., wrote of a legendary pond in the area of Argos, called Lake Lerna in some sources, or the Alkyonian Lake.

The depth of the Alkyonian lake is limitless, nor do I know anyone who was ever able by any contrivance whatever to reach down to the bottom. Nero tied together many, many fathoms of rope, with a hanging lead weight and every kind of useful device for experiment, but he was unable to discover any limit to its depth (Pausanias ii.37.5).

Pausanias also spoke in the same passage of the mysteries of the legendary pond which “drags down anyone who dares to swim across it and sucks him into the depths.” He also states that it was at Lerna where Herakles defeated the Hydra, a monster that had been hiding under a plane tree near the spring of Amymone (ii.37.4).

One of the primary objectives of the geoarchaeological work in the Argive Plain was to establish the geological record of the former lake in order to reconstruct its age and extent, and to determine whether the distribution of archaeological sites was related to it.

Among the 19th-century travellers, Dodwell (1819: 224–228) was the first to pay attention to the many tales about this former lake. In a chapter entitled “The Lake of Lerna,” he carefully listed the relevant historical sources (Herodotus, Strabo, and Pausanias) and described the portrayals of the “Lernaean Hydra” with its varying number of heads. Comparing all these with his own observations of the 19th-century landscape, he drew the conclusion that the lake itself must have been the Hydra that “entered the plain and ravaged the country and the flocks” (Dodwell 1819: 226). The ever-renewing heads of the Hydra, to Dodwell, would have been the streams feeding the lake. When Herakles attempted to stop these streams by blocking their springs, the waters soon vented elsewhere. Dodwell also surmised that the number of Hydra’s heads varied because the number of streams which fed Lake Lerna varied with the seasons. His views were repeated by other scholarly travellers in the plain (e.g., Thiersch 1866: 64) and soon became the conventional wisdom.

The Hydra can also be seen as an allegory for the malaria peril represented by mosquito eggs that may have hatched

in the pool, and which had threatened the people of Lerna and Nauplion for several millennia. Dodwell described the malaria fevers raging there (1819: 222, 247) and was later killed himself by an infection incurred on his journeys. Herbert Lehmann (1937) also described the unhealthy Argive Plain and the yellow faces of Nauplion’s citizens stemming from hepatitis. He became infected by typhus during his work in the Argolid.

Angel’s (1966, 1971) studies of the human bones from Lerna suggested that malaria was common there since at least the Bronze Age. He described porotic hyperostosis, an unusual growth of blood-producing bone marrow, that can result from sickle-cell anemia and thalassemia. The alterations of hemoglobin that are the cause of these two diseases impede malarial infection and also produce extra resistance against malaria, however. The percentage of people suffering from sickle-cell anemia and thalassemia therefore increases because of the reduced viability and death from malaria among individuals with normal hemoglobin. If a large ratio of skeletons show porotic hyperostosis the conclusion can be drawn that malaria was widespread. Angel (1972) argued that malaria befell the eastern Mediterranean especially from the Mesolithic to middle Bronze Age and again from Hellenistic to Roman times.

Although Lake Lerna was said to be bottomless it eventually disappeared. Old topographic maps still show the lake but they seem to be based on the written reports (and on each other) rather than on field observations; maps from the early 16th century, for example, show the lake much farther north, near Mycenae. Several maps of the late 17th century, on the other hand, put the lake properly near Lerna. In the 19th century travellers found a lake but were disappointed by its small size, and the last map to show standing water in the area was made by Lehmann (1937). Shortly after that the road from Nauplion to Mili, a modern village near Lerna, was finished and the draining of the area behind the road was intensified; apart from a swamp that becomes flooded during heavy winter rains, no traces of Lake Lerna remain.

Regional Geology and Physiography

The relief of the Argive region is determined by the tectonic setting. The plain is a graben system bound by prominent faults (Angelier 1978; Dewey and Şengör 1979; Le Pichon and Angelier 1981). Major tectonic movements in the Peloponnese took place during the Pliocene and early Pleistocene periods (Schröder and Kelletat 1976), and recent investigations have shown that block movements continued throughout the Quaternary and that some faults are still active (van Andel, Zangger, and Perissoratis in press). The plain lies at the boundary be-

tween two Hellenide zones, both of which are members of the central Hellenic nappe and thus belong to the same regional geological unit as the area around Volos (Jacobs-hagen 1986). The Pindos zone, stretching westward from Lerna and including the Artemision mountain range, consists mainly of pelagic sediments including Cretaceous limestone, Jurassic chert, and middle Triassic limestone, flysch, marl, and diabase (Bannert and Bender 1968; Bachmann and Risch 1979). The two valleys NW and SW of Lerna (FIG. 5) are cut into otherwise continuous bedrock west of the fault. These valleys contain alluvial fans of early to middle Pleistocene age characterized by an intensive red color.

One borehole was placed a few hundred meters south of Lerna and 20 m away from the seashore. At a depth of 6 m it penetrated a sequence of yellow and brown paleosols interlayered with dark gray marine mud. Both paleo-

sol and marine mud contained abundant marine microorganisms (Zangger and Malz 1989) dating back to the early Pleistocene, pointing towards considerable tectonic uplift in this area. The Pleistocene deposits continue to be at the surface in Lerna and west of the road from Lerna to Argos. One auger core, taken near the shore in Mili, penetrated only highly consolidated Pleistocene paleosols. Hence, the landscape around the Bronze Age site of Lerna has not been significantly altered by Holocene sedimentation. The 1.5 m-high shore cliff SE of Lerna provides further evidence of an erosional rather than an aggradational environment, and Lerna could have been somewhat farther from the sea when it was first settled.

Maps at a scale of 1:5000 with 0.5 m contour intervals reveal how the topography of the Argive Plain itself is mainly controlled by sediment accumulation along the Inakhos River (FIG. 6). Around Argos the surface deposits

Figure 6. Topographic map of the coastal part of the Argive Plain with 0.5 m contour intervals. Levees of overbank loam accumulated along the Inakhos. The 0.5 m contour west of the Inakhos River mouth emphasizes the beach barrier as well as the lowland behind it. No sediment has accumulated along the Erasinos because its suspended load is trapped during its long path underground.

Figure 7. Section through Holocene and Pleistocene sediments between Magoula and the sea. A Pleistocene paleosol occurs at the bottom of all cores and at the surface west of the section. On the seaward side of the profile a paleo-surface (A horizon) is preserved on top of the Pleistocene base. The existence of Lake Lerna is represented by thick and extensive lacustrine deposits. The lake was separated from the open sea by a beach barrier. Only limited alluviations occurring in the Early Bronze Age were found in this traverse (EH-All.). Paleo-A-horizon (dark layer on top of EH-All.) indicates landscape stability.

consist entirely of overbank loams and floodplain deposits laid down by episodic Inakhos floods. Several meters of such usually fairly recent and undisturbed silts can be found in the cut banks of the stream, together with frequent debris flows and slump deposits. The result is a levee system of overbank loam rising above the eastern and western parts of the backshore (FIG. 6). Although levees are not discernible in the field, they dominate the contour pattern as a shallow but broad alluvial cone. No delta has developed at the Inakhos' mouth, however; instead the coastline cuts across the contours along the stream as a result of longshore current transport of material eroded from the mouth of the Inakhos during long intervals of nondeposition. Because of this westward longshore drift the beach east of the Inakhos's mouth is essentially free of gravel whereas the western shore consists only of gravel. The redeposited sediment accumulates along the shoreline and forms a beach barrier that separates the wetland NE of Lerna from the coast (FIGS. 6, 7). The westward transport also involves fine-grained mate-

rial; after heavy rains in the winter a yellow cloud of suspended sediment forms where the Inakhos meets the sea and travels slowly westward even when the wind is blowing from the south and sw.

Holocene Stratigraphy

A 3 km-long, straight traverse of eight auger and two drill cores, the deepest reaching 17 m, was placed across the western coastal plain extending from the ancient site of Magoula to the present coast (FIG. 7). Not surprisingly, the Pleistocene alluvial fans that form the land surface west of the road from Mili to Argos continue eastward in the subsurface. There, the Pleistocene surface is buried under younger deposits that gradually increase in thickness to reach 6.0–6.5 m near the present coast. In the core samples, the fan surface appears as a well consolidated red bed (2.5YR to 7.5YR) with pedogenic calcite concretions larger than 1 cm in diameter. This hard fan surface could not be penetrated with a handcoring device because of its high degree of consolidation. The upper boundary of the

red paleosol is sometimes sharp and erosional, but in most core holes a clay-rich A horizon up to 1 m thick and dark brown in color (10YR4/1 to 10YR3/4) is preserved above it. The A horizon is full of roots and charcoal; pottery fragments and a high phosphate content suggest human activity.

Subaqueous deposits cover the alluvial fan surface and its A horizon over most of the profile and consist of homogeneous, bluish gray (5BG4/1)-to-black clay, intercalated with 10–20 cm thick peat and humus layers and thin horizons enriched in gastropod fragments. Although the quiet-water origin of the deposit is obvious, determining the precise paleoenvironment and especially the paleosalinity required micropaleontological study of selected samples. Finke (1988a) and Finke and Malz (1988) have shown that the clay deposits contain almost exclusively autochthonous populations, including ontogenetic suites, of the freshwater ostracods *Ilyocypris* and *Candona*. The deposit therefore originated in a freshwater environment that, according to calibrated radiocarbon dates (6330 ± 100 B.C., 4660 ± 120 B.C., 3820 ± 100 B.C.) and sherds of the very early Bronze Age, covered the western half of the coastal plain from the early Holocene onwards. The earliest Holocene alluvial deposit occurs in the western part of the section near the site of Magoula. Up to 3 m thick, this unconsolidated, dark yellowish-brown (10YR4/4) alluvium, of silty texture, contains undiagnostic potsherds in the uppermost 50 cm and Early Helladic ones on its former surface. A buried A horizon is preserved locally on top of the alluvium, indicating postdepositional land stability. Since lake deposits are partly superimposed on the alluvium, the latter must antedate the time when the lake reached its maximum size.

Lacustrine sediments occur at the surface over a wide area, indicating that the lake remained an open body of water until recently. The alluvium crops out on the landward side of the traverse, but in most places the uppermost 0.4 to 1.1 m of both units seem to have been altered by humans. One drill hole was placed about 30 m from the coast, where it penetrated 5.5 m of homogeneous gravel deposits with well rounded, well sorted, grain-supported pebbles several centimeters in diameter. The base of the gravel was not reached. The gravel deposits represent a beach barrier that separated the lacustrine environment from the open sea. Samples taken from the test hole contain organisms that lived on the seaward side of the barrier: fish, foraminifera, and marine gastropods and ostracods.

South of Argos, a trench several kilometers long was dug in 1987 for a water supply pipeline, providing an opportunity to confirm the core results in an exposed

profile (FIG. 8). The trench was 5.5–6.5 m deep and trended w-e, thereby crossing the contact between Pleistocene red beds and floodplain or subaqueous deposits. The stratigraphic sequence begins with a paleosol several meters thick that correlates with the Pleistocene alluvial fans and with the Pleistocene base found in the drill holes. This paleosol is characterized by a well developed structure, thick clay films, and red color (5YR3/4). It is covered by dark gray subaqueous deposits (5Y4/1 mottled with 10YR3/2) that contain Early Helladic I sherds. The overlying alluvium is characterized by a mottled dark yellowish-brown color (10YR6/4 and 10YR4/4), and contains fragile pedogenic calcite nodules of 3–4 mm in diameter, and fragments of land snails and Early Helladic II sherd fragments. The upper boundary of the alluvium is very sharp, because the surface had become stable at this time and underwent incipient soil formation before another subaqueous unit similar to the lower one and with the same color (5Y4/1 mottled with 10YR3/2) was laid upon it. The base of this deposit is enriched with charcoal pieces containing Early Helladic sherds. It is evident that the Lernaean Lake represented by the two lacustrine beds silted up during the Early Helladic because of increased sediment input from soil erosion.

Along the foot of the hills the lake deposit is covered with up to 2.1 m of colluvium. The colluvium is poorly sorted, homogeneous, and does not show soil development, although the lower part of it is slightly better consolidated. It contains many randomly distributed sherds, predominantly of Classical and Hellenistic age. What seems to have been a Classical house was found in this colluvium about 1 m under the main road to Argos. The complex stratigraphy in the trench, especially the displacement of the Pleistocene and overlying subaqueous deposits, indicates uplift of the mountain ranges in the west relative to the coastal part of the plain. As a result lake deposits occur up to 2 m above modern sea level. The Early Helladic alluvium in Figure 7 and the Pleistocene base in Figure 8 also are displaced 2.5 m corresponding to a movement rate of 0.5 m/1000 years (Finke 1988a: 103; van Andel, Zangger, and Perissoratis in press); similar rates have been observed elsewhere in Greece (Fabricius 1984: 823; Flemming 1978).

Reconstruction of Lake Lerna

A marine seismic reflection survey has shown that the Argive Plain extended 10 km farther south during low glacial sea level (van Andel, Zangger, and Perissoratis in press). When the polar caps began to melt 15,000 years ago, the coast shifted gradually landward to a position beyond the present one. On the east side of the Argive

Figure 8. An exceptionally large trench (1.5 km long, 6 m deep) provided the opportunity to verify the auger core data. At the base is a Pleistocene paleosol covered by dark gray lacustrine deposits belonging to the Lernaean Lake and containing Early Helladic I sherds. Subsequently, alluvium dated by the presence of many Early Helladic II sherds filled the lake. It is covered in turn with another lacustrine layer indicating a second lake stage. The final layer is a colluvial deposit containing many dispersed Classical and Hellenistic sherds. A Classical house (C/H) was found in this colluvium about 1 m under the main road to Argos. The complex stratigraphy in this trench is assumed to represent an uplift of the mountain ranges in the west relative to the coastal plain. It should be noted, however, that the vertical scale is ca. 40X exaggerated; the displacement of the Pleistocene base is, in reality, much shallower.

Plain the sea came close to Tiryns; on the west side, a large freshwater lagoon, Lake Lerna, formed, separated from the sea by a barrier beach built by sediments carried to the sea by the Inakhos River and dispersed by longshore currents. The perennial water supply by the Erasinos River kept the lagoon fresh as is evident from microorganisms retrieved from the lacustrine sediments.

In the subsurface the lake sediments extend all the way to the outskirts of Argos, 4700 m from the present coastline. Despite its large size, the lake was not very deep. The lacustrine sediments are maximally 6.0–6.5 m thick and the actual water depth of the lake must have been less than that. Peat found at 7.2 m and dating back to 6330 ± 100 B.C. represents the first swamps and marshes that developed behind the barrier beach, and complete isolation from the sea is indicated by the absence of marine microfossils at the base of these lagoonal deposits. Around 4660 ± 120 B.C. the lake must have been close to its

maximum size, because peat of that age was found in 3.6 m depth near the prehistoric site of Magoula.

In the Neolithic, when Lerna was settled, the sea was still rising, and the coast was probably a few hundred meters away from the site. During the Early Bronze Age, when Magoula and Argos were established, much of the southern Argive Plain was initially covered either by the sea or by freshwater, and both settlements were near the shore of the freshwater lagoon. Later in the Early Bronze Age, however, this lagoon, Lake Lerna, was largely filled because of major soil erosion in the drainage of the Inakhos River (Finke 1988a: 138).

The location and maximum extent of the vanished lake were confirmed by Niemi and Finke (1988) and Finke and Malz (1988) using a 1972 Landsat-1 image of the Peloponnese. The occurrence of porotic hyperostosis in human bones led Angel (1966; 1972: 100) to suggest two Holocene wet phases for southern Greece, one from

ca. 7000–2000 B.C. corresponding to the final stage of the sea level rise, and one from A.C. 100–400. The soil stratigraphic profile (FIG. 8) shows that Lake Lerna did indeed have two phases of maximum extent that coincide with Angel's dates. A maximum age for the second phase of increased marshiness was provided by a Hellenistic house that was found just below the upper lacustrine deposits sw of Tiryns (Finke 1988: 139). The drying of the marsh south of Lerna was also reported by Aristotle (quoted by Schliemann 1885: 29):

At the time of the Trojan war the land of Argos was marshy, and could only support few inhabitants; the land of Mycenae, on the contrary, was good and highly esteemed. Now, however, the opposite is the case, for the land of Mycenae is dried up, and therefore lies idle; while the land of Argos, which was a marsh, is now good arable land.

The stories about the "bottomless" depth of Lake Lerna and the mythological comparison with Hydra reflect the threat felt by the local inhabitants. Although the cause of malaria was not known in the Bronze Age, people must have been aware that the residents of villages as little as a few kilometers inland did not suffer from malaria, and, likely, efforts were made to improve conditions. Curtius (1851) related in the middle of the last century how people attempted to utilize the swamp. He found an artificially dammed lake with an overflow conduit used to drive a water mill. Later the farmers drained the wetland, evidently by reducing the course of the Erasinos and by planting trees in a systematic fashion. Today only a small area of wetland remains, and that is being filled in with waste. Standing water, which floods the houses near the beach, only appears after heavy winter rains.

Conclusions

The similarities between the present Gulfs of Volos and Argos outlined in the introduction (arable land fed by ephemeral streams and encompassed by steep, barren limestone mountains) are evidently based on a similar geological history: both areas belong to the same regional geological unit, both are affected by recent tectonic movement, and both have experienced a similar geological history in the Holocene. In both areas, the most recent landscape changes have been dominated by a transgressive/regressive cycle. The transgression was caused by the post-glacial sea level rise and thus induced by nature, whereas the regression was coupled with extensive soil erosion and probably induced by humans. Different conditions of deposition and current, however, caused the development of a beach barrier on the western side of the Argive Plain while the bay at Dimini stayed connected with the open sea. Consequently, after the maximum transgression, the

shore at Dimini regressed gradually from its peak position, whereas the coastal part of the Argive Plain went through a more complex development. In addition, the maximum transgression at Dimini was during the Neolithic, preceding the Early Bronze Age maximum at Lerna by a millennium or more, because the peak position of any transgression depends not only on the rate of sea level rise, but also on the rate of sedimentation in the coastal zone (Curry 1964). At Dimini soil erosion began at the time of the Dimini Culture in the Neolithic, whereas in the Argive Plain, it occurred in the Early Bronze Age (Finke 1988a: 109). In both areas, the increased sediment supply exceeded the continuing rise of the sea and regression of the shore began.

The ancient cultural prominence of the two areas can be attributed to their advantageous geographic settings. Coastal plains provide easy beach access and often also natural harbors, besides plentiful arable land, springs, and streams. Many of the site locations in both areas were dependent on this favorable environmental setting. The settlements of Dimini, Magoula, Lerna, and Iolkos were placed where small streams met the sea or lake shore. When the environment changed, in these cases through shifts in sea and lake shores, some sites were abandoned and new ones established elsewhere. It should be noted, however, that shifts of regional centers do not always imply environmental change; economic and political factors alone may be sufficient to account for them.

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